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Exploring legal frameworks for climate action: a network analysis of Green Deal, EU Directives, and environmental assessment indicators

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Abstract. The analysis focuses on investigating the links established between climate and environmental policies within the key policy instruments of the European Union (EU). The specific research objective was to gain a better understanding of the structural relationships between the EU's climate policy and environmental policy agenda. Using a network perspective to visualize how climate and environmental policies intersect, we identified some of the key climate governance policy instruments and explored the areas of connections and disconnections between them. A dataset of 30 key climate and environmental policy instruments was collected, and they were classified into three main policy instrument categories: climate policies, circular economy policies, and pollution control and biodiversity protection policies. The network analysis also recorded centrality measures to provide an insight into how the policy instrument was interconnected to the policy network and what type of relationships existed between them. Additionally, K-core clustering provided a measure for identifying whether the policy instrument served as an indicator of the roles of key actors in climate-related policies. Our findings highlight that key policies in the network, such as the European Green Deal and EU-ETS, serve as central points of coordination for a variety of sustainability policies. We found that there may be potential complementary governance reflected in the significant overlap around waste and pollution control, yet further study is required to assess the implications of functional redundancy. This research provides valuable information about the relationships within the network of climate and environmental policies and the synergies and gaps within the EU's sustainability agenda overall.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) leads environmental governance efforts on a global scale and recognizes that climate action requires immediate attention [1]. The EU has developed the European Green Deal and other policies to tackle climate change, promote sustainable resource use, and establish a fair transition to new energy systems. The EU's legal instruments can achieve their effectiveness through their individual provisions and how these provisions develop in relation to each other as part of the broader policy constellation. Modern policy analysis now emphasizes how different regulatory frameworks connect to each other when addressing climate change [2]. Network analysis has proven itself to be an important method for studying complex policy relationships by showing how different legal instruments either support or conflict with each other. Network analysis is widely used in the literature to better understand complex policy connections and interactions, and, in this article, we specifically use this tool in climate governance to reveal the links between legislative tools.

Environmental assessment indicators are instruments used by the EU to measure the effectiveness of policies within its framework for climate action. The outcomes of various projects can be assessed using these criteria, which include carbon emissions reductions, habitat and species conservation, and energy efficiency [3]. Recent studies have emphasized the need to improve the policy-related environmental indicators to provide a more comprehensive and accurate picture of how climate policy affects a variety of outcomes [4]. The body of research on an environmental assessment method that is more flexible and iterative, and incorporates feedback to enhance future policies, in addition to ongoing result monitoring, is expanding.

This study employs a network analysis to gain a deeper understanding of the co-evolution of EU climate policy. By investigating key EU policy tools like the European Green Deal, key EU directives, and environmental assessment indicators through network theory, this study examines the legislative frameworks that serve as the foundation for climate action in the EU [5]. To better evaluate these policies' overall function within the larger legislative framework, the research will concentrate on their relationships and interactions. This study also considers how well assessment indicators work to measure the efficacy of policies and monitor progress toward sustainability goals [6].

This study uses network theory to map and examine the interdependencies in the legal framework in order to find the gaps or multilayer governance for climate action. Through the mapping and analysis of interdependencies in the legal instruments, this effort will contribute to the discussion on how to improve climate governance in the EU. The results could be helpful to decision-makers in identifying areas with better coordination and proper environmental governance.

2. Methodology

The primary dataset consists of the 30 most important EU climate and environmental policies, selected after careful legislation review. The policies were chosen for their importance in the legal system and legal force (e.g., Directives, Framework Directives), as well as their role as part of a wider action for climate change within the EU (e.g., strategies, action plans). We use systematic document analysis and cross-referencing of relevant EU policy documents and selected them by considering the following four criteria: (i) legal binding, (ii) directly relating to EU climate and environmental objectives, (iii) recency and relevance of policy (2020-2025), and (iv) the presence of measurably defined assessment indicators. Furthermore, we considered three general categories of policy: (i) Climate Policy Instruments (this includes EU-wide regulation such as the European Green Deal, and the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), with immediate impacts on emissions and efforts towards a low-carbon economy; (ii) Circular Economy Policies (policies which focused on resource efficiency, waste management and the circular economy, such as the Circular Economy Action Plan will be examined for their efforts towards sustainable resource use) and Pollution Control / Biodiversity Protection Policies (the third category is defined by directives and regulations to control pollution and retain biodiversity. Both the Industrial Emissions Directive and the EU Biodiversity Strategy fall under this category. For the policy instruments included in this study, we have identified measurable assessment indicators outlined in the policy documents to signal relatedness and primarily assess the effectiveness of these indicators to achieve sustainability objectives. There may also be representations of the sample policy instrument with varying legal contexts, such as regulation or another summarily binding commitment.

The sample also includes policies with distinct legal frameworks, ranging from regulations with binding commitments to voluntary frameworks or non-legally binding recommendations. The main tool of analysis for this research is network analysis, which allows for the analysis of policy instruments and their relationships in the EU climate governance context. In this analysis, emphasized linkages due to a shared actor, objective, or evaluation indicator. This approach allows for a better understanding of the interactions between policies and their collective impact on climate action.

We first created a two-mode network [7] by mapping policy connections with their assessment indicators and metrics. In this way, we investigated the relationship between the European Green Deal and the EU Emissions Trading System with predefined environmental indicators, such as CO₂ emissions reductions, energy efficiency improvements, and waste recycling rates. For this network, we calculate

centrality metrics such as betweenness centrality, to identify and illustrate the most influential policies within the network and associate assessment indicators. Policies with high betweenness centrality [8] are those that serve as key bridges between different groups of policies, potentially playing a crucial role in shaping the EU's climate strategy. Other network measures, like degree centrality [9] and eigenvector centrality [10], will also be considered to highlight the interconnectedness and influence of individual policies, but a policy having fewer links does not necessarily mean it lacks indicators or impact.

The next step in our analysis was to highlight the most important actors and their collaboration for the implementation of the investigated policies. For this analysis, we performed K-core clustering to highlight the brokers within the network. Using software tools like igraph, Ucinet [11] or Netdraw [12], the relationships between policies will be visualized, creating an easy-to-understand map of the regulatory network. These visualizations will help identify clusters of policies that work together and highlight any gaps or redundancies in the EU's climate action framework. In this way, we provide a detailed view of how various EU climate policies are interconnected and how they collectively contribute to achieving the EU's climate goals. The analysis will also point out areas where coordination can be improved or where policies may inadvertently conflict or overlap.

3. Results of the Network Analysis on EU Climate and Environmental Policies

3.1. Network Structure and Policy Interlinkages.

The two-mode network representation (Figure 1) and centrality results (Table 1) reveal how different EU policies are interlinked based on shared assessment indicators. The policies within the European Green Deal and the Fit for 55 Package are central to the network, with several connections to various emission reduction, energy efficiency, and resource management indicators. Circular Economy Action Plan emerged as a key node, linking with several other policies through waste management, emission reduction, and energy efficiency indicators. Both indicated policies also have a high eigenvector score, indicating that they are well connected to other influential policies in the network. This shows their role as key drivers in influencing other sustainability measures. From the betweenness centrality point of view (best position in the network), high values are registered for the European Green Deal, that serve as a crucial bridge between different policy clusters and playing a central role in shaping broader climate action as they facilitate connections across multiple goals and initiatives. On the other hand, regarding the evaluation indicators assessed, Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions Reduction (%) is by far the most central indicator, had the highest values for degree (0.233), betweenness (0.087), and eigenvector centrality (0.388). Energy Efficiency Improvement (%) (degree: 0.167; betweenness: 0.048; eigenvector: 0.357) and the Renewable Energy Share (%) (degree: 0.167; betweenness: 0.076; eigenvector: 0.337) had strong centrality metrics, establishing closely related connectivity and illustrated their importance, given that these indicators underpin EU sustainability. The Share of Energy from Low-Carbon Sources (%) (degree: 0.133; betweenness: 0.033; eigenvector: 0.334) is in top four and has relevance through related reference to policy, enabling policymakers to prioritise action towards denser low-carbon policies. Our results illustrate that emission reduction and energy efficiency are front and centre in the EU climate governance policy architecture.

3.2. K-core Clustering in Actors' Collaboration Network.

The K-core analysis of the actors' collaboration network shows who the key actors are in the EU's implementation of its climate and environmental policies. The network shows the European Commission and National Governments are core actors (shown in cyan squares) that are particularly critical to linking and connecting other private and public stakeholders, such as environmental NGOs, regulators, and sectors [13].

Table 1. Centrality metrics for top 10 investigated policies

<i>Top 10 policies according to normalized centrality</i>	Degree	Betweenness	Eigenvector
<i>European Green Deal</i>	0.3	0.175	0.642
<i>Fit for 55 Package</i>	0.25	0.14	0.587
<i>Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR)</i>	0.075	0.123	0.057
<i>Circular Economy Action Plan</i>	0.125	0.092	0.003
<i>Renewable Energy Directive (RED III)</i>	0.125	0.051	0.185
<i>Smart and Sustainable Mobility Strategy</i>	0.125	0.047	0.173
<i>Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan</i>	0.05	0.039	0.031
<i>Hydrogen Strategy for a Climate-Neutral Europe</i>	0.1	0.032	0.186
<i>Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR)</i>	0.1	0.023	0.163
<i>Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy</i>	0.05	0.02	0.073

Figure 1. Network visualization of key EU climate and environmental policies (green squares), grouped by related assessment indicators (orange circles). Size of nodes by betweenness centrality score.

The European Commission also acts as a hub to connect several types of sectors, such as the Energy Sector, Manufacturers, and Financial Institutions, which signals its very active role in forming and implementing policies. Similarly, National Governments also display a high level of centrality, most especially to Energy Regulators, Water Utilities, and environmental NGOs. These two core actors of the compressed collaboration network of actors tend to represent core coordination entities across multiple domains across the network, with central placement. The outer layer of the network (in yellow) shows other types of actors like the Private Sector, Transport Sector, and Chemical Industry, who are still linked to the core but do not possess the same situational centrality as the Commission or National Governments. Other actors, like Environmental NGOs and marine conservation NGOs, are relatively central but still highlight the role of NGOs working in the environmental sector connected to policy implementation.

The analysis further highlights robust teamwork between sectors, such as Energy Companies, Construction Industry, and Forestry Industry, which can reflect clusters of aligned industries cooperating

on regulatory compliance. The K-core clustering displays a well-spread conglomerate with hierarchical ties in their connections, and public institutions, such as the European Commission, act as brokers linking academic research with industry, NGOs, and regulators, in order to ensure the policies are incorporated across sectors. The selected policies collectively target crucial sustainability metrics such as reductions in CO₂ emissions, energy consumption, and waste. The indicators most frequently associated with these policies, such as GHG Emissions Reduction and Energy Efficiency Improvements, suggest that the EU's policy framework is heavily geared towards mitigating climate change through both direct emission reductions and increased energy efficiency. However, the analysis also pointed to areas where policy goals may overlap or conflict, particularly in resource management and energy use, suggesting a need for further alignment of indicators to avoid inefficiencies.

Figure 2. One-mode network representing the collaboration established between key stakeholders involved in policies implementation (color of nodes by K-core clustering, size by betweenness centrality scores).

4. Discussion on environmental policy interactions

The core role of the European Green Deal and the EU ETS indicates that these policies are key drivers of EU climate action [14]. Furthermore, the simultaneous existence of overlapping policies in areas like waste management and pollution prevention indicates the need to pursue a more cohesive policy framework, one that reduces redundancy and sets out a clear, complementary role. The weak connections established between climate policies and biodiversity conservation highlight a potential area for improvement. Considering present environmental challenges [15], addressing climate change while safeguarding biodiversity is essential for achieving long-term sustainability. The EU could strengthen climate and biodiversity synergies [6], for example, by incorporating biodiversity indicators into climate action strategies. In terms of assessment indicators, the study finds that while some policies have well-defined metrics, others require more robust and comprehensive indicators to evaluate their impact effectively. Moving forward, the EU should prioritize the development of more precise and adaptable assessment tools that can capture the multifaceted nature of climate action, particularly in the areas of biodiversity and sustainable development.

While the network shows strong interconnectivity between key policies, there are some gaps where certain policies, especially those relating to biodiversity protection and pollution control, are less connected to the broader climate framework. On the other hand, some areas, such as energy efficiency and GHG reduction, have a high concentration of policies with overlapping objectives, potentially leading to redundancies. This indicates a need for streamlining in these areas to enhance coordination.

Given the centrality of policies like the European Green Deal, further coordination among clusters, especially in the areas of biodiversity and pollution control, is necessary. Enhancing the connectivity between these areas and broader climate action could improve their effectiveness [16]. Some assessment indicators, particularly those in waste management and pollution sectors, could benefit from clearer definitions to help avoid any potential overlap. A more streamlined assessment could make measuring and achieving sustainability goals more efficient. The impact of policy varies depending on where it is implemented nationally, and there is a clear need to implement and monitor key indicators related to sectors like energy and waste management. Network analysis can provide valuable insights, but it cannot capture the complete complexity of EU policy interactions in general, and certainly not those relating to soft law or informal mechanisms. The effectiveness of indicators can also differ based on how they are implemented nationally. For the sake of robustness, we limited the study to those policy actions with definitive, measurable results.

5. Recommendations for policy coordination

The analysis yields several recommendations for strengthening the EU's climate governance. Increased coordination of central policies can improve efforts to coordinate central policies in key initiatives, such as the European Green Deal, the EU Emissions Trading System, and the Renewable Energy Directive. Addressing overlapping environmental policies will contribute to reducing inefficiencies [17]. Streamlining circular economy policies and pollution control regulations would eliminate duplicated efforts. A clearer delineation of responsibilities among existing policies and a stronger integration of circular economy measures into broader climate policies would contribute to advancing coherence among policies. Connecting climate action and biodiversity protection is essential. Integrating biodiversity objectives and indicators into climate policies, where possible, such as within the EU Emissions Trading System, would promote a more holistic environmental approach. Developing comprehensive assessment indicators is necessary for policies that currently lack clear and measurable benchmarks. Introducing more robust environmental indicators would improve the ability to track progress and support informed climate governance decisions. Enhancing monitoring capacity is another key step. Experts in climate governance recognize the importance of expanding monitoring efforts to assess progress effectively. Strengthening the capacity to track a range of climate indicators would allow for a more systematic evaluation of governance outcomes.

6. Conclusion

This research demonstrates a thorough examination of the EU's framework for climate action via a network analysis mapping of key legal instruments that make up that framework, such as the European Green Deal, the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), and the Circular Economy Action Plan. It shows that, while overarching policies such as the European Green Deal and the EU ETS are important anchor points in the policy framework network for delivering climate action, there are different levels of overlap of additional policies (e.g., in pollution or waste management) which suggest some duplication, redundancy, and inefficiency of how those policies work together in delivering coordinated climate action by the EU. The analysis also showed that the integration of biodiversity conservation is not represented in the climate policy network, and while perhaps this could use to be improved regardless of the action, the EU will undertake on climate change, they might want to make sure they are improving links between mitigation of climate change and biodiversity conservation. The analysis offers insights into the several different but interconnected climate and environmental policies the EU has created and how those contribute to their shared sustainability goals. The EU might also derive improved opportunities for overall effectiveness of sustainability policies and connections by enhancing or better aligning assessment indicators. Future research could investigate how policy networks in the EU are dynamic by assessing changes in the landscape of EU climate governance. It would also be valuable to research the effectiveness of cross-sector policy initiatives, for example, combining climate action with agricultural policies to further both climate objectives and rural development.

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